

Effectiveness Of Legal Aid Service Application For Victim Of Crime In Early Childhood

Fatin Hamamah, Didi Sukardi

Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 29, 2021

Accepted:
July 30, 2021

Keywords :

Effectiveness of
Application, Legal Aid
Service, Crime in Early
Childhood

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5148841

Abstract

This research aims to develop legal aid services applications for victims of crimes in early childhood. Use methods with a mixed-method approach. The qualitative approach systematically, factually, and accurately describes images, or paintings, of facts or phenomena under investigation. While the quantitative approach to test the effectiveness of applications developed. Random sampling techniques take samples based on a certain level, with many respondents as many as 75 people. Qualitative data analysis techniques began to record the regularity of patterns (in theoretical notes), explanations, causal flows, and propositions. Make conclusions loosely, stay open, and be skeptical. While with the quantitative approach, data analysis is done with a description of the percentage of questionnaire results. The findings of the study regarding the use of legal aid applications that practical applications in providing legal assistance services to early childhood by 89.5%.

Introduction

The practice of frequent crimes, especially to children, is essentially an unlawful act. A crime is an unjustified act and contrary to the laws and regulations of all States and all religions (Time, Payne and Gainey, 2010; Cross, 2020; Sibisi and Warri, 2020). To overcome, at least avoiding acts that lead to crime is through the educational process. Education becomes a means that is considered appropriate and effective in fostering children's morals and ethics. Early childhood is an age where they still have total dependence on adults (Jonsson and Williams, 2013; Thulin and Jonsson, 2014) because they are not yet independent. They are also very vulnerable to crimes committed by adults.

Relevant research suggests that strengthening the legal position in children is essential because the work is much weaker than adults (La Fors, 2020). It is necessary to provide access to justice for children's needs for sectarian violence and abuse (UNICEF and UNODC, 2015). Protective services in each state are guided by law, although the path to legislation is different for each area to facilitate full service that benefits victims (Jackson, 2017). Now child sexual abuse is increasingly being recognized as a crime (Heisler, 2012; Kohn, 2012; Jackson and Hafemeister, 2016), and victim services expanded to include victims of sexual abuse (Stoltenborgh *et al.*, 2011; Mignot *et al.*, 2018; Wekerle *et al.*, 2018). The South African country has made strides in protecting children in conflict with the law to better protect and ultimately for safer communities (Sibisi and Warri, 2020).

Based on some of the previous research opinions that have been presented above need to provide legal assistance to victims of crimes against children. The rapid development of information technology needs to be utilized to facilitate legal aid to victims of crime. The application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in various fields has become a service tool for improving work efficiency and productivity (Marszk and Lechman, 2021). The legal aid sector is one of the community's services to strengthen ICT to improve its performance. ICT applications have the potential to identify and find solutions to provide convenience in legal aid services to the broader community (Bhattacharjee and Shrivastava, 2018).

This research aims to develop legal aid applications for victims of crime at an early age. The rise of crimes against early childhood makes researchers interested in providing legal assistance that facilitates users. This application is expected to provide legal assistance as soon as possible. The problem formulation is the practical application of legal aid service for victims of crime in early childhood? The focus of the problem is developing Android-based apps to be downloaded for free through the play store. The novelty of this research is the use of information technology as a legal aid service facility against crimes in early childhood.

Method

Sample techniques

The sampling technique is a way to determine the number of samples according to the sample size that will be used as the actual data source, taking into account the properties and spread of the population to obtain a representative sample (Sugiyono, 2016). Random sampling techniques take samples based on a certain level. Based on the results of sampling techniques, the number of respondents was as many as 75 people. The research was conducted in 5 districts of Cirebon, West Java, namely Palimanan, Klangean, Arjawinangun, Astanajapura, and Babakan.

Research design

The research method used in this study is mixed-method research. A qualitative approach is used so that the discussion is by the focus of the intended scope. Qualitative descriptive research is researching an object to systematically, factually, and accurately describe, describe, or paint regarding facts or phenomena under investigation. While the quantitative approach to test the effectiveness of applications developed.

Data Collection Techniques

To obtain various data related to research, the qualitative approach using 4 (four) stages. First, editing is a re-examination ranging from completeness, conformity, and relevance to issues related to research. The second is coding, which is providing notes that state the type of source (books, journals, research, and so on). Furthermore, reconstructing, namely reordering the research source materials regularly and logically, is easy to understand and interpret. Moreover, the systematization is to place materials sequentially based on the systematic framework of discussion that refers to the sequence of problems. In contrast, the robust approach with the presentation description of the questionnaire is distributed to respondents through the Likert scale. The instruments used with a score scale of 5 strongly agree, four agree, three are neutral, two disagree, and one strongly disagree.

Data Analysis Techniques

Qualitative data analysis techniques began to record the regularity of patterns (in theoretical notes), explanations, causal flows, and propositions. Make conclusions loosely, stay open, and be skeptical. While with quantitative approach, data analysis is done with a description of the percentage of questionnaire results

Results and Discussion

Based on the results of the data analysis obtained from a questionnaire shared through google form with the first research question: What is the most critical problem related to the use of legal aid applications in your opinion? When asked about the use of the app, respondents discussed the main issue is the ease of providing information, meaning in reporting crimes quickly and easily. There is no need to travel to the city to visit the legal aid office; just from home, the information can be delivered. But there are obstacles for respondents who live in the village because of the availability of internet networks not to access the application. In this case, the lack of access to the necessary instruments such as smartphones, tablets, or computers for respondents living in the village. The first question that the application developed makes it easier for victims of crime to obtain legal aid. Several researchers support his statements; the information system makes it easier to convey information (Hutchison and Mitchell, no date; Nachiketa *et al.*, 2013; Kumar, 2017; Raghavendra *et al.*, 2018; Riaño Galán *et al.*, 2018; Tayebi *et al.*, 2019).

The second question about legal aid applications is “the user’s unawareness of information and communication technology.” Undoubtedly, the effective use of any information and communication technology requires knowledge and information on using it. Respondents who filled out the questionnaire stated that there needs to be training or a menu of guidance on using the application because the community in the community has difficulty using the application.

This course is vital because those who experience crimes are primarily children living in the village. Therefore, academies need to socialize legal aid applications so that the public can understand and operate them. Based on this second question that legal aid applications are practical in provide services to victims of crime. This opinion is supported by previous researchers that information and communication systems are effective in facilitating

information (Ghobakhloo *et al.*, 2012; Zubair, Miankhel and Nawaz, 2013; Ghavifekr and Rosdy, 2015; Ratheeswari, 2018).

Before the application was tested, researchers made pre observations about application services that the average respondent has used. Almost all respondents have been 98% using the service application, but about shopping services, paying taxes, paying electricity accounts, banking applications. In contrast, for legal services applications hamper 100% have never used it. After socialization and training following the preliminary survey results, a questionnaire instrument was given regarding the use of legal aid applications, as for the results as in table 1.

Table 1. Respondents' perception of legal aid applications

Question	Verry Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly disagree (%)
The use of legal aid applications is beneficial in crime complaints	69.03	22.39	7.84	0.75	0
The use of legal aid apps makes it easier to file crime complaints	62.98	25.95	10.31	0.76	0
The use of legal aid applications significantly increases public attention to legal services.	71.43	16.54	11.28	0.75	0
The use of legal aid apps motivates victims to get justice	68.18	21.21	9.09	1.52	0
Legal aid apps are designed interactively and dynamically.	66.29	24.24	7.95	1.52	0
Access to legal aid apps is effortless to operate	70.37	22.22	6.67	0.74	0
Legal aid apps have live feedback.	67.92	21.13	10.19	0.75	0
The use of legal aid applications is very effective in serving victims of crime.	68.19	21.31	9.29	1.21	0

As shown in Table 1, legal aid applications are beneficial in criminal complaints considered useful in legal services. Thus, 91.42% strongly agree with this statement, 7.84% are neutral, and 0.75% disagree. Regarding legal aid applications and their effectiveness in providing legal assistance services to early childhood, 89.5% of respondents strongly agreed and agreed, while 9.29% were neutral and 1.21% disagreed.

Respondents also expressed perceptions about using legal aid applications significantly increased public attention to legal aid services. Most of them expressed strongly agreed and agreed with 87.97% that legal aid applications can increase public engagement to legal aid services. However, 11.2% of respondents were neutral, and only 0.75% disagreed.

Respondents also expressed perceptions about the use of legal aid applications motivating in obtaining justice. Most of them strongly agree and agree with 89.39% that legal aid applications encourage victims to get justice. However, 9.09% of respondents declared neutral, and only 1.52% disagreed. These findings align with research conducted by (Lim, Lee, and Guan, 2010) which emphasizes that legal aid services can motivate victims to obtain justice.

Regarding the use of legal aid applications designed interactively and dynamically to provide legal assistance services to victims of crime, 90.53% of participants expressed strongly agreed and agreed. In comparison, 7.95% were neutral, and 1.52% disagreed. Regarding access to legal aid, applications are straightforward to operate, which shows that 92.59% of respondents strongly agree and agree, while neutral by 6.67% and disagree 0.74%.

That legal aid application had direct feedback based on the results of the poll analysis that 88.26% of respondents expressed strongly agreed and agreed, while the neutral ones were 10.23% and disagreed 0.75%. Respondents also said perceptions about using legal aid apps helped make it easier to raise criminal complaints about legal aid. Based on the explanation, it can be presented with graphics such as figure 1.

Figure 1. Perception Poll Results Respondent to the use of Legal Aid Applications

Conclusion

The use of legal aid service applications helps victims of crime obtain justice. Based on the feedback results, better performance when given legal aid applications the number of complaints to get legal aid services. Respondents considered the use of legal aid applications could motivate victims of crime to obtain justice. This app encourages victims to become active to obtain justice, thus increasing the motivation of crime victims to dare to report crimes to get justice. The legal aid service application is easily accessible because it is available in the Play store can be downloaded for free.

An essential factor for remote interaction and the process of getting legal aid services quickly. In addition, low assistance service application is easy to use because it uses plug and play system, can update automatically following the smartphone system, and offers immediate results.

The limitations of this research have not evenly distributed internet network infrastructure facilities in Indonesia, so there are constraints in accessing the application. Crimes against children occur in many remote areas, so more research is needed to think of new technologies to reach remote locations or new applications matching the room.

References

- Bhattacharjee, A. and Shrivastava, U. (2018) 'The effects of ICT use and ICT Laws on corruption: A general deterrence theory perspective,' *Government Information Quarterly*, 35(4), pp. 703–712. DOI: 10.1016/j.giq.2018.07.006.
- Cross, M. K. D. (2020) 'International Journal of Law, Crime and Justice Counter-terrorism & the intelligence network in Europe', *International Journal of Law Crime and Justice.*, (November 2019), pp. 1–9. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijlcj.2019.100368.
- La Fors, K. (2020) 'Legal Remedies For a Forgiving Society: Children's rights, data protection rights and the value of forgiveness in AI-mediated risk profiling of children by Dutch authorities,' *Computer Law and Security Review*, 38, p. 105430. DOI: 10.1016/j.clsr.2020.105430.
- Ghavifekr, S. and Rosdy, W. A. W. (2015) 'Teaching and learning with technology: Effectiveness of ICT integration in schools,' *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 1(2), pp. 175–191. DOI: 10.21890/ijres.23596.
- Ghobakhloo, M. et al. (2012) 'Strategies for successful information technology adoption in small and medium-sized enterprises,' *Information (Switzerland)*, 3(1), pp. 36–67. DOI: 10.3390/info3010036.
- Heisler, C. (2012) 'Elder abuse and the criminal justice system: An uncertain future,' *Generations*, 36(3), pp. 83–88.
- Hutchison, D. and Mitchell, J. C. (no date) *Electronic Government - EGovGlossary*. Available at: http://userp.uni-koblenz.de/~egov/wiki/index.php?title=Electronic_Government#_note-Lucke.
- Jackson, S. L. (2017) 'Adult protective services and victim services: A review of the literature to increase understanding between these two fields,' *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 34, pp. 214–227. DOI: 10.1016/j.avb.2017.01.010.
- Jackson, S. L., and Hafemeister, T. L. (2016) 'Theory-based models enhancing the understanding of four types of elder maltreatment,' *International Review of Victimology*, 22(3), pp. 289–320. DOI: 10.1177/0269758016630887.
- Jonsson, A. and Williams, P. (2013) 'Communication with young children in preschool: the complex matter of a

- child perspective,'*Early Child Development and Care*, 183(5), pp. 589–604. DOI: 10.1080/03004430.2012.678488.
- Kohn, N. A. (2012) 'Elder in Justice: A Critique of the Criminalization of Elder Abuse,'*American Criminal Law Review*, 49(1), pp. 1–29.
- Kumar, N. (2017) 'Use of Information Communication Technology (ICT) and Library Operation : An Overview,'*International Conference on Future Libraries: From Promises to Practices*, pp. 445–455.
- Lim, C., Lee, T. and Guan, C. (2010) 'Effectiveness of a brain-computer interface based program for treating ADHD: a pilot study,'*Psychopharmacol Bull*, 43(1), pp. 73–82. DOI: 10.4324/9781315853178.
- Marszk, A. and Lechman, E. (2021) 'Reshaping financial systems: The role of ICT in the diffusion of financial innovations – Recent evidence from European countries,'*Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 167(May 2020), p. 120683. DOI: 10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120683.
- Mignot, S. et al. (2018) 'Child Abuse & Neglect Identifying teenage sexual abuse victims by questions on their daily lives,'*Child Abuse & Neglect*, (March), pp. 0–1. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2018.07.027.
- Nachiketa, K. et al. (2013) 'Developing an Android Based Learning Application,' (1), pp. 36–38.
- Raghavendra, P. et al. (2018) "'I like talking to people on the computer": Outcomes of a home-based intervention to develop social media skills in youth with disabilities living in rural communities,'*research in developmental disabilities*, 76(December 2017), pp. 110–123. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2018.02.012.
- Ratheeswari, K. (2018) 'Information Communication Technology in Education,'*Journal of Applied and Advanced Research*, 3(S1), p. 45. DOI: 10.21839/jaar.2018.v3is1.169.
- Riaño Galán, I. et al. (2018) ' statement by the Spanish Paediatric Association about gender diversity in childhood and adolescence: Ethical and legal view from a multidisciplinary perspective', *Anales de Pediatría (English Edition)*, 89(2), pp. 123.e1-123.e6. DOI: 10.1016/j.anpede.2018.02.003.
- Sibisi, M. and Warri, A. (2020) 'Challenges experienced by probation officers working with children in conflict with the law in the Johannesburg Metro Region (South Africa),'*Children and Youth Services Review*, 113(November 2019), p. 104949. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.104949.
- Stoltenborgh, M. et al. (2011) 'A global perspective on child sexual abuse: Meta-analysis of prevalence worldwide,'*Child Maltreatment*, 16(2), pp. 79–101. DOI: 10.1177/1077559511403920.
- Sugiyono (2016) *Qualitative, Quantitative and R&D Research Methods*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Tayebi, S. M. et al. (2019) 'The role of information systems in communication through social media,'*International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 3(3), pp. 245–268. DOI: 10.5267/j.ijdns.2019.2.002.
- Thulin, S. and Jonsson, A. (2014) 'Child Perspectives and Children ' s Perspectives – a Concern for Teachers in Preschool,'*Educare*, 2, pp. 13–37.
- Time, V., Payne, B. K. and Gainey, R. R. (2010) 'Don't help victims of crime if you don't have the time: Assessing support for Good Samaritan laws,'*Journal of Criminal Justice*, 38(4), pp. 790–795. DOI: 10.1016/j.jcrimjus.2010.05.006.
- UNICEF and UNODC (2015) 'Treatment of Child Victims and Child Witnesses of Crime.'
- Wekerle, C. et al. (2018) 'The utility of Twitter as a tool for increasing reach of research on sexual violence,'*Child Abuse, and Neglect*, 85(April), pp. 220–228. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2018.04.019.
- Zubair, M. K., Miankhel, A. K. and Nawaz, A. (2013) 'Information & Communication Technology and "Individual": Prospects & Concerns,'*Global Journal of Computer Science and Technology Network, Web & Security*, 13(7), pp. 1–10.

Author Information

Fatin Hamamah

Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Cirebon
Perjuangan Street No.17, Karyamulya, Kec. Kesambi,
Kota Cirebon, Jawa Barat 45131

Didi Sukardi

Institut Agama Islam Negeri SyekhNurjati Cirebon
Perjuangan Street, Sunyaragi, Kec. Kesambi, Kota Cirebon,
Jawa Barat 45132
